

Development of Contextual Learning Methods in Islamic Religious Education Learning

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ABSTRACT

This study is intended to examine the urgency of developing PAI learning methods from conventional to contextual. The study in the research, among others, discusses the basis of the development of learning methods, the characteristics of conventional learning methods, and the characteristics of contextual learning methods. The method used in the research is a literature study of primary sources and secondary sources, in the form of previous research results which are research reports and articles published in scientific journals. The results showed that to increase the effectiveness of PAI learning, it is necessary to shift from conventional methods to contextual methods. With contextual methods, teachers can relate PAI materials to real situations, illustrate their relevance in everyday life, and encourage students to bridge theoretical knowledge with its application in their lives. The use of contextual methods in PAI learning in schools is an innovative effort to enhance the role of Islamic education in educational institutions, with the main objective of forming Islamic character in students. The study recommends that PAI teachers can apply contextual methods in PAI learning so that the results of PAI learning can be more meaningful for students' lives.

INTRODUCTION

Education generally aims at discovering human nature. Education also serves to facilitate the process of becoming a complete human being. Islam, as a revealed religion, contains universal teachings that cover all aspects of life. Therefore, the researchers found that there is a clear harmony between the goals of national education and Islamic education, showing similarities in vision and mission in the process of producing intelligent student outcomes with high moral integrity. He emphasizes that. This is the aim of Islamic Religious Education (hereinafter abbreviated as PAI) to help students strengthen their Islamic faith, devotion, awareness and practice, to believe in Allah SWT, to be dedicated to Him and to become Muslims with a noble spirit. It is based on the fact that it is intended to become. Personality in private life, society, state, and nation (Fatimah, Damaianti, Ningsih, & Gusniawati, 2023).

Islamic education can be interpreted as individual and community education, because the teachings of Islam contain the attitudes and personal behavior of the community towards the welfare of individual and collective life and emphasize more and more on mental improvement which will be realized in good deeds for oneself and others. Islamic education is an effort in the form of guidance and care for students so that later, after completing their education, they can understand and practice the teachings of Islam as a way of life (Firmansyah, 2022). In this context, education is an effort to bring students to maturity in various aspects, both in cognitive, affective, and psychomotor aspects. Education is not just teaching that emphasizes the process of transferring knowledge, but is a transformation of values and personality formation with all the aspects it covers through certain methods (Ali, 2023). This is where learning methods become important to always be developed.

The development of learning methods from conventional to contextual certainly has many aspects behind these changes. In Arabic, method is *thariqah*, which is strategic steps prepared to do something work and purpose. The achievement of educational goals cannot be separated from the role of the learning method process. The learning process has the goal of achieving each subject taught. Islamic education in its learning process undergoes a metamorphosis in the form of the learning methods it uses (Zamista, Faridah, Rahmi, Liwa, Maula, Wangsadanureja, & Arifin, 2022). Islamic education learning methods that are often used are lectures. This type of method is done by conveying information orally. This method is known as the most practical and economical way (Firmansyah, 2016). This is related to the use of this method which does not require tools. This method is generally used to overcome the problem of literature scarcity. As well as information sources that are difficult to reach by students and others (Helmi, 2016). As for contextual learning, it is based on the belief that in the learning process a person will be interested in learning by seeing the meaning of what he is learning. In contextual learning, students will gain meaning in knowledge and skills, leading to the development of children's knowledge and skills in finding meaning from each learning process (Ali, 2021).

The transformation of learning methods from conventional to contextual learning is a very innovative thing in the development of Islamic education today. The implementation of contextual learning for PAI, according to Azyumardi Azra, as cited by Mailani (2019), is a process of preparing human resources to run life and fulfill their life goals more effectively and efficiently. Islamic education must continue to strive to be able to provide new things and renewal in the implementation of learning. There are quite a lot of researches related to the development of PAI learning methods, such as the researches of Qowim (2020) and Firmansyah (2022). In that context, the development of Islamic education learning methods, according to Ahyat (2017), is very important to do because it will have a positive and significant impact on PAI learning outcomes. In this position, research takes a role, namely to enrich the scientific treasure of the urgency of this research study.

THEORETICAL REVIEW

Etymologically, the method in Arabic is known as *thariqah*, which means strategic steps prepared to do a job. When connected with work or education, the method must be realized in the educational process, in order to develop mental attitudes and personalities so that students receive lessons easily, effectively and can be digested properly (Firmansyah, Ali, & Romli, 2022). Teaching method is a method used by teachers in conducting relationships with students during teaching. The teaching method is a tool to achieve the teaching objectives to be achieved, so that the better the use of teaching methods, the more successful the achievement of goals, meaning that if the teacher can choose the right method tailored to teaching materials, students, situation conditions, teaching media, the more successful the teaching objectives to be achieved (Mailani, 2019).

A good teaching and learning process must be in accordance with learning principles. Learning principles according to Larsen and Freeman are the theoretical framework of a learning method. Theoretical frameworks are theories that direct how a method should be viewed in terms of: 1) materials to be taught, 2) learning procedures (how students learn and how teachers teach materials), 3) teachers who teach, and 4) students who are taught (Sitorus, & Nazaruddin, 2021; Zulkipli, Hidayat, Ibrahim, & Praja, 2020). With this model, teachers can help students get or acquire information, ideas, skills, ways of thinking, and expressing their own ideas. In addition, the learning model also teaches how they learn.

The right learning will certainly give good results. Likewise, in the application of learning methods, there are several things that become the rationale for choosing learning methods, namely: 1) religious basis, 2) biological basis, 3) psychological basis, and 4) sociological basis. *First*, the religious basis, meaning that the methods used in Islamic education learning must clearly be based on religion. This is because Islam refers to the Qur'an and Hadith, which consists of faith (aqidah), Islam (fiqh), and ihsan (morals). So, the use of methods must be based on these religious foundations (Khoerunnisa, Akil, & Abidin, 2022).

Second, the biological basis (physical basis), the physical development of each individual/student is very influential on the learning process. For example: students who are deficient in vision (nearsighted), when learning should be placed in the front seat. This condition also affects the selection of methods to be used in learning. *Third*, the psychological basis (spiritual basis), in addition to biological development, the psychological development of each individual/student must be different. So that in using learning methods, a teacher must pay attention to the psychological/spiritual/psychological conditions of students. When we determine a biologically based method, it must still be reconsidered from the psychological side. Which in the psychological aspect consists of: motivation, emotions, interests, talents, attitudes, skills. *Fourth*, the sociological basis, aspects related to the environment in which the individual/student is located. The environment is one of the aspects that influence the choice of learning methods. For example, the method conveyed by Wali Songo in preaching Islam in Indonesia is certainly different from other scholars who convey Islam not in Indonesia (Khoerunnisa, Akil, & Abidin, 2022).

METHODOLOGY

This research is a library research, which limits research activities based only on library collections, which intends to collect information related to the development of PAI learning methods using contextual models based on literature studies from various expert views. The primary source of research comes from research results published in the form of research reports and scientific articles. The secondary data sources come from various books and journal articles relevant to this research. The research data collection was carried out using documentation techniques. The data analysis uses inductive analysis.

RESEARCH RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Conventional Islamic Education Learning Methods

Conventional learning methods are traditional learning. As Paulo Freire terms conventional learning patterns "banking concept" in which students are filled and crammed with various subject matter. Learners only accept everything they receive from educators without any critical thinking. Conventional learning has certain characteristics, namely: (1) not contextualized, (2) not challenging, (3) passive, and (4) the learning materials are not discussed with the learners. In the teaching and learning process, the teacher dominates (Hamid, & Hadi, 2020). Conventional learning or also called the classical learning approach is a learning pattern that emphasizes the power of educators in learning. This classic learning pattern has been criticized by most people. Even so, learning patterns are still widely used by teachers. Conventional learning is less demanding in terms of facilities and infrastructure so it is more likely to be implemented. The subject matter presented can be classical so it does not require high costs. The learner can automatically apply the theories obtained in the classroom in everyday life. The purpose of the Islamic learning method is an effort to be able to increase student success in the

learning process. In the process of learning religion, methods have an important role in providing teachings of divine values. So that learning methods have an important role in student success.

According to Zaini, & Marsigit (2014), conventional learning has characteristics that distinguish it from other learning concepts, namely as follows:

1. Learners are passive recipients of information, where learners receive knowledge from the teacher and knowledge is assumed to be standardized information and skills.
2. Learning is individualized.
3. Learning is very abstract and theoretical.
4. Behavior is built on habit.
5. Truth is absolute and knowledge.
6. The teacher is the determinant of the learning process.
7. Good behavior is based on extrinsic motivation.
8. Interaction among learners is lacking.
9. The teacher often acts inattentive to the group processes taking place in the study groups.

In the context of PAI learning, some forms of conventional methods that are often used include: lecture, question and answer, discussion, assignment, experimentation, demonstration, tutorial/guidance, and problem solving. Based on this description, when viewed from the model of delivering learning messages, the implementation of conventional learning more often uses the provision of information compared to demonstrating and providing opportunities for direct performance by students. In other words, teachers more often use a one-way pattern by strictly following the sequence of material in the curriculum (Fahrudin, Ansari, & Ichsan, 2021). In this condition, teachers assume that the success of the learning program is seen from the completion of delivering all the material in the curriculum. In fact, what actually becomes the benchmark for achievement is the students' achievement of learning objectives.

Contextualized Islamic Education Learning Methods

Contextual Islamic education learning method is learning that is carried out under real situation conditions, this concept provides learning where the teacher will connect the material with real conditions or situations, so that it can encourage students to be able to connect between the knowledge they have and its application in students' daily lives. The relationship involves seven main components in effective learning, namely: constructivism, questioning, discovery, learning community, modeling, and authentic assessment. As Johnson, defines contextual learning as an educational process that aims to help students see the meaning in the learning materials they learn by connecting them with the context of their daily lives, namely with the context of their personal, social and cultural environment (Kadir, 2013). This kind of contextual learning method emphasizes students to see, feel, hear and experience what is conveyed by educators in the real world.

Contextual learning is built based on the influence of the philosophy of constructivism. How an educator is able to condition, create a learning atmosphere that makes it easy for students to understand, interpret and be able to connect the subject matter they learn (Mailani, 2019). In practice, according to Budiman (2017), contextual learning has several forms in its implementation, namely:

1. Linking, used when the teacher relates a new concept to something the students are already familiar with. Clearly, linking what students already know with new information.
2. Experiencing is the core of contextual learning where linking means connecting new information with experience or knowledge of new information with previous experience. Learning can happen more quickly when students utilize (manipulate) equipment and materials and conduct active forms of research.
3. Applying is a form of learning used when students apply concepts in learning activities to solve problems, teachers can motivate students by providing realistic and relevant exercises.
4. Cooperating is applied when students who work together in groups usually find it easier to overcome complex problems with little help than students who work individually. The experience of working together not only helps students learn the learning material but is consistent with the real world.
5. Transferring means that the teacher's function and role in this context is to create a variety of learning experiences with a focus on understanding rather than memorization.

In that regard, according to Jannah (2015), contextual learning has certain characteristics, which are as follows:

1. Learning is carried out in an authentic context, that is, learning that is directed towards the achievement of skills in the context of real life or learning that is carried out in a natural environment (learning in real life setting).
2. Learning provides opportunities for students to work on meaningful tasks (meaningful learning).
3. Learning is carried out by providing meaningful experiences to students (learning by doing).
4. Learning is carried out through group work, discussion, mutual correction between friends (learning in a group).
5. Learning provides opportunities to create a sense of community, work together, and understand each other deeply (learning to know each other deeply).
6. Learning is carried out actively, creatively, productively, and prioritizes cooperation.
7. Learning is carried out in a fun situation.

Based on the description above, it can be concluded that the contextual method is very suitable to be applied in PAI learning because this method focuses on students' understanding, development of knowledge, skills and

contextual understanding of the relationship between subjects and what students encounter in their daily lives. Especially when looking at the material in PAI learning which has all three elements of cognitive, affective and psychomotor. The use of contextual approach in PAI learning as one of the alternative methods in the development of PAI learning in schools is actually an effort to further enhance the role of Islamic education in schools in order to form students with Islamic character. Broadly speaking, the fundamental differences in learning using conventional methods with contextual methods are as described below.

Table 1. Differences between Conventional Learning Methods and Contextual Methods

No.	Conventional Method	Contextual Method
1	Places students as learning objects who act as passive recipients of information	Placing students as learning subjects means that students play an active role in every learning process by finding and exploring the subject matter themselves
2	Students learn more individually by receiving, recording, and memorizing subject matter	Students learn through group activities, such as group work, discussion, receiving and giving
3	Learning is theoretical and abstract	Learning is linked to real life in real terms
4	Ability acquired through practice	Ability based on experience
5	The ultimate goal is grades and numbers	The ultimate goal is self-satisfaction
6	Individual actions or behaviors are based on factors from outside themselves, for example individuals do not do something because they are afraid of punishment, or simply to get numbers or grades from the teacher	Actions or behaviors are built on self-awareness
7	The truth that is owned is absolute and final, because knowledge is constructed by others	The knowledge possessed by each individual always develops in accordance with the experiences they experience, therefore each student can differ in interpreting the nature of their knowledge
8	The teacher is the one who determines the learning	Students are responsible for monitoring and developing their own

	process	learning
9	Learning only happens in the classroom	learning can take place anywhere in different contexts and settings according to needs
10	Learning success is usually only measured by tests	Learning success is measured in a variety of ways, for example by process evaluation, student work, performance, etc.

Source: Kadir (2013); Sapiudin, Nata, & Syihab (2016).

In connection with the above, there are five important characteristics in the contextual PAI learning process that are not owned by conventional learning methods, namely: *First*, contextual PAI learning is a process of activating existing knowledge (activating knowledge), meaning that what will be learned is inseparable from the knowledge that has already been learned, thus the knowledge that students will acquire is intact knowledge that has a connection with each other. *Second*, contextual PAI learning is learning in order to acquire and add new knowledge (acquiring knowledge). The new knowledge is obtained in a deductive way, meaning that learning begins with studying the whole, then paying attention to the details. *Third*, understanding knowledge, meaning that the knowledge obtained is not to be memorized but to be understood and believed, for example by asking for responses from others about the knowledge they have obtained and based on these responses, the knowledge is developed. *Fourth*, practicing knowledge and experience (applying knowledge) means that the knowledge and experience gained must be applied in students' lives, so that changes in student behavior can be seen. *Fifth*, reflecting knowledge on the knowledge development strategy. This is done as feedback for the process of improving and refining the strategy (Sahlan, 2011).

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The development of PAI learning methods in the direction from conventional to contextual needs to be done by teachers. Through contextual methods, teachers will connect the material with real conditions or situations, so as to encourage students to be able to connect the knowledge they have with their application in everyday life. The utilization of contextual methods in teaching PAI in the school environment is an innovative step in enhancing the role of Islamic education in these educational institutions. This is done with the main purpose of forming Islamic character in students, and is one of the alternative methods used in the development of PAI learning in schools.

The research recommendations refer to the hope that PAI learning activities are directed towards orientation towards learning objectives, one of which is through the application of contextual learning methods. So that the results of PAI learning are not just students memorizing religious propositions, but also students are skilled in applying the results of the learning in everyday life. This will positively significantly create religious students, who display good and correct behavior in life in the midst of society.

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